

The Challenge

Conventional wood-based panels such as particleboard and MDF rely on fossil and formaldehyde-based adhesives. The wood panel industry urgently needs sustainable, high-performance alternatives that reduce environmental impact without compromising quality or cost.

Our Innovation

SUSBOARD develops and demonstrates 100% bio-based and formaldehyde-free adhesives for industrial wood board production as a substitute for fossil-based adhesives.

Objectives

Replace traditional fossil-based adhesives with 100% bio-based alternatives.

Develop and scale up a formaldehyde-free, bio-based adhesive.

Enhance the sustainability without compromising on quality.

Lower carbon footprint of the wood boards by up to 30%.

Expected Impacts

Environmental:

Cuts CO₂ emissions by up to 30% and reduces formaldehyde & VOC emissions.

Economic & Industrial:

Delivers TRL7 bio-based adhesives, scaling up to 1,000+ tons post-project.

Societal:

Enables affordable, sustainable furniture and healthier indoor air.

Scientific Coordinator:

Wood K plus
e.herwijnen@wood-kplus.at

Project Coordinator:

RTDS Group
susboard@rtds-group.com

The Result

a sustainable,
high-performance adhesive
ready for industrial implementation

Consortium

Duration: 2025 – 2029

Total budget: 9.1M

EU contribution: 6.9M

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